

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: STEERING AND STIMULATING ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOURS OF LEARNERS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA

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Keywords:

Entrepreneurship education, Educational enablers, Government policy, Learners in private universities, Entrepreneurial behaviours.

Abstract: *Entrepreneurial behaviours have been identified as a pertinent driver of innovation, job creation and economic growth globally. Thus, Entrepreneurial behaviours are viewed as critical to the survival of every entrepreneurial endeavour worldwide and higher education institutions are recognised as major channels for steering and stimulating these behaviours. However, Entrepreneurial behaviour have been vitiated as evidenced by the lack of capital, entrepreneurial skill gaps, technological skill gaps, intense competition, regulatory challenges and limiting belief. These challenges have continued to attract the attention of notable gamut of scholars and policymakers. Existing literature indicates that entrepreneurship education is suggestive of addressing these challenges. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of entrepreneurship education on Entrepreneurial behaviours of undergraduate students in higher education institutions Nigeria-wide. Survey research design was adopted. The population was 3,025 final-year undergraduate students from four selected private universities in Nigeria. A sample size of 341 was determined using Krejcie and Morgan formula. Stratified random sampling method was adopted in selecting the respondents. Validated questionnaire was administered for data collection. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients for the constructs ranged from 0.71 to 0.87. A response rate of 95.1% was achieved. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential (multiple and hierarchical*

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regression) statistics at a 5% level of significance. Findings revealed that entrepreneurship education dimensions had a significant effect on entrepreneurial behaviours of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria. The study concluded that entrepreneurship education affects the entrepreneurial behaviours of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria. The study recommended that the management of selected universities should cooperate with government and regulators to provide adequate funding, grants and support for learner's startups and innovative projects so as to engender positive entrepreneurial outcomes.

1.0 Introduction

Entrepreneurship is often seen as a pivotal enabler of prosperity and a pertinent driver of economic growth and development of developing and developed nations. Notably, in the past, the world experienced the potent effect of entrepreneurship in job creation, poverty reduction and economic growth (Oluwasanya, 2026). In tandem, worldwide economic downturn has affected organizational competencies, capabilities, strategies, focus and the educational sector which made it germane for government, policy regulators and top management of higher education institutions to have a paradigm shift about the way things are done (Musa, 2026). Most importantly, the world needs turbo-charged global leaders and proactive educational systems that will nurture and equip current and future generations of entrepreneurs with the venturesomeness required to succeed and mentor others (Oluwasanya, 2026). In the last decade, there has been growing interest in formulating and

stimulating policies and programs to promote and support the idea of entrepreneurship as an attractive alternative to wage employment among learners (potential entrepreneurs) around the globe (Musa, 2026). The reasons being that learners (potential entrepreneurs) are expected to through qualitative entrepreneurial teaching and learning steered and stimulated with focus on entrepreneurial behaviours towards identifying unmet market needs and creating new business outlets to provide such needs profitably. Secondly, entrepreneurs are identified as potent drivers of positive economic and social outcomes. Thirdly, qualitative entrepreneurial teaching and learning are regarded as stimuli for entrepreneurial success, economic growth and development of any nation (Oluwasanya, 2026). Particularly, the world is becoming an international marketplace of ideas, talents and opportunities. There is no doubt that institutionalizing and stimulating entrepreneurship education has been one of the

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key policy objectives for the developing and developed economies worldwide (Musa, 2026). Entrepreneurship education has gained the attention of policymakers, practitioners, and researchers (Boubker et al., 2021; Ratten & Usmanij, 2021; Tiberius & Weyland, 2023). Entrepreneurship education plays a key role in domestic economic development and building a business (Boldureanu et al., 2020; Galvão et al., 2020; Martínez-Gregorio et al., 2021; Walmsley & Wraae, 2022). A pertinent vitiating element with entrepreneurship education is the inability to adequately stimulate entrepreneurial intention (EI) and action. Several factors might contribute to this failure, such as transforming entrepreneurial ideas into practice and manifesting theories into real life business outlets (Oluwasanya, 2026), entrepreneurial praxis (Le Loarne Lemaire et al., 2022), a supportive environment, and the ability to acquire the right entrepreneurial skills (Sastre et al., 2021). Additionally, cognitive style is crucial in understanding entrepreneurial behaviour (Marques et al., 2021). Worldwide, due to the highly recognised value of entrepreneurship, governments have made entrepreneurship a priority and created an entrepreneurial ecosystem that includes entrepreneurship education, policy support, funding and a favourable operating milieu that encourages its learners particularly university learners, to establish new business ventures. For example, in Nigeria, government encourage

and support higher education institutions to integrate entrepreneurship into their curriculum to stimulate enterprising behaviour and foster entrepreneurial spirit (Musa, 2026). The introduction of entrepreneurship education by the Government of Nigeria through the National Universities Commission (NUC) in 2006 was the intervention strategy in line with global trends to refocus university education towards entrepreneurship education as well as to combat the persistent rise in graduate unemployment. It was therefore no surprise that the Federal Government of Nigeria, through the National Universities Commission (NUC), introduced Entrepreneurship Education (EE), which is aimed at equipping tertiary students with entrepreneurial skills, attitudes and competencies in order to be job creators and not just job hunters. Most importantly, higher education institutions play an important role through qualitative entrepreneurial teaching and learning and stimulating paradigm shift by learners to think entrepreneurially out of the box towards achieving consistently consistent entrepreneurial outcomes (Oluwasanya, 2026). Incontrovertibly, entrepreneurship education is taught in all of the study programs at the universities in Nigeria. The goal is for the university to induce entrepreneurial thinking in their student. Therefore, universities are expected to be able to offer effective and impactful entrepreneurship education modules (Boubker et al., 2021). Thus, entrepreneurship

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education can be conceptualized as “a purposeful intervention by an educator in the life of the learner to impact entrepreneurial qualities and skills to enable the learner to survive in the world of business” (Olokundun et al., 2017). However, learners prefer paid employment to self-employment (Oluwasanya, 2026). Despite this growing interest and offerings, students tend to have less interest to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Adelaja et al., 2023). In this study, we are exploring how learners perceive entrepreneurship education and its relationship with entrepreneurial behaviour (EB). We applied Ajzen's attitude scaling methods, which assume that the attitude toward a specific behaviour is a hypothetical construct that must be inferred from three categories of measurable responses, including behavioural, cognitive and affective responses (Ajzen, 2005). These three types of attitudinal responses reflect negative or positive evaluations of the attitude object (i.e., ATEE). Ajzen (1991) stated that the collection of specific behaviours observed on different occasions and situations represents a more valid measure of the underlying behavioural disposition than any single behaviour. In studies on entrepreneurship education, attitude towards entrepreneurship education (ATEE) has been ignored (Lee & Wong, 2003). Therefore, we investigated this issue by treating attitude towards entrepreneurship education (ATEE) as a higher-order multidimensional construct with

three conceptually distinct components, including behavioural, cognitive and affective components. In this study, we aimed to answer the following questions: How does learner's attitude toward entrepreneurship education directly affect their entrepreneurial behaviour? How does attitude toward entrepreneurship education shape entrepreneurial behaviour indirectly through attitude toward entrepreneurial action?

This study contributed to the existing entrepreneurship literature in three ways. First, our study highlighted the importance of entrepreneurship education in promoting the entrepreneurial behaviours of learners in Nigeria. Second, it showed the multidimensionality (behavioural, affective, and cognitive) of attitude toward entrepreneurship education. Third, the study also answered prior questions concerning the effect of attitude toward entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial behaviour of learners and the mediating role of educational enablers and government policy.

2.0 Statement of the Problem

Higher education institution's learners in Nigeria have not been able to translate their entrepreneurial learning experience positively into the achievement of future entrepreneurial missions, visions and positive outcomes (Oluwasanya, 2026). Despite the introduction of entrepreneurship education as a compulsory course in Nigerian higher education

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institutions, the aspirations for paid employment and graduate unemployment had consistently been on the increase. This indicates that the exposure to entrepreneurship education through qualitative teaching and learning will trigger and stimulate entrepreneurial behaviours of learners towards achieving positive entrepreneurial outcomes (Oluwasanya, 2026).

The upsides of entrepreneurship education to the learners and the nation cannot be overemphasized. Some of these include an increase in employment, particularly self-employment, an increase in productive capacities, innovation and creativity, financial literacy, increased income streams, among others (Musa, 2026). Despite these benefits, the Nigerian landscape is beset with many factors that militate against the effective steering and stimulating entrepreneurial behaviours through entrepreneurship education higher education institution-wide (Oluwasanya, 2026). These challenges have continued to attract the attention of scholars and policy makers. These limiting factors includes lack of passion and commitment by the government and management of universities, inadequate funding, increasing cost, focus on theory-driven teaching methods instead of firsthand qualitative teaching and turning out graduates who are not trained to be self-reliant (Ojeifo, 2012). Also, inadequate infrastructural facilities

and educational enablers, lack of competent and experienced educators, irrelevant and outdated curriculum, absence of counselling and orientation on the importance of entrepreneurial skills, lack of awareness of entrepreneurship education, volatile business environment, unstable social and political climate, absence of credit policy that addresses the specific needs of enterprises, insufficient provision of funds by the government, increase in graduate unemployment, economic downturns and lack of concrete plans that can address the existing gaps in entrepreneurship education Nigeria-wide (Lee et al., 2021; Ubogu, 2020; Amadi & Eze, 2019; Rasheed, 2018; Onigbinde, 2018; Usoro, 2018; Adesanya, 2017). It has been revealed that one of the challenges with our educational system is that students in universities and polytechnics are not acquainted with the necessary information to be influential entrepreneurs. Several studies (Omoniyi & Gamede, 2022; Azolike et al., 2021; Nwachuckwu et al., 2021; Abioye, 2020; Oruku, 2015; Undiyaundeye & Ekpungu, 2015) posited that these institutions focus on impacting knowledge for current white-collar jobs instead of impacting knowledge and skill to be job creators and individuals that can improve already existing businesses. Therefore, it becomes imperative to explore the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial behaviours

Table 1. Summary of Table of Hypotheses Tested

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Hypotheses	Models	Results	Remarks
Ho ₁	Entrepreneurship education components have no significant effect on possibility mentality of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria	If $\beta_1 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₂	Entrepreneurship education components have no significant effect on proactive abilities of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria	If $\beta_2 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₃	Entrepreneurship education components have no significant effect on turbo-charged passion of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria.	If $\beta_3 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₄	Entrepreneurship education components have no significant effect on innovativeness and creativity of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria.	If $\beta_4 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₅	Entrepreneurship education components have no significant effect on risk-taking attributes of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria.	If $\beta_5 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₆	Educational enablers have no significant moderating effect on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial behaviours of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria.	If $\beta_6 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
Ho ₇	Government policy has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial behaviour of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria.	If $\beta_7 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected

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Ho8	Educational enablers and government policy have no significant combined moderating effect on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial behaviours of learners in higher education institutions in Nigeria.	If $\beta_8 \neq 0$ & $p \leq 0.05$	Rejected
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(Musa and Oluwasanya, 2026)

3.0 Operationalization of the Variables

In this study, the variables are classified into three: the independent, dependent variable and the moderating variables. The Independent variables (X) is entrepreneurship education measured by sub-variables of entrepreneurial culture, entrepreneurial mindsets, entrepreneurial capacities, entrepreneurial attitudes and entrepreneurial skills while the dependent variable (Y) is entrepreneurial behaviour measured by possibility mentality, proactive abilities, turbo-charged passion, innovativeness and creativity, risk-taking attributes; and the moderating variables (z_1, z_2) are educational enablers and government policy. The operational model for the study variables is denoted in the equations below:

$Y = f(X)$

$Y = f(XZ)$

Y= Dependent variable

X= Independent Variable

Z= Moderating Variables (z_1, z_2)

Y= Entrepreneurial Behaviours

X= Entrepreneurship Education

Z_1 = Educational Enablers (EE) = Moderating Variable

z_2 = Government Policy (GP) = Moderating Variable

$Y = (y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5)$

$X = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$

$Z = (z_1, z_2)$

y_1 = Possibility Mentality

y_2 = Proactive Abilities

y_3 = Turbo-Charged Passion

y_4 = Innovativeness and Creativity

y_5 = Risk-taking Attributes

x_1 = Entrepreneurial Culture

x_2 = Entrepreneurial Mindsets

x_3 = Entrepreneurial Capacities

x_4 = Entrepreneurial Attitudes

x_5 = Entrepreneurial Skills

Z_1 = Educational Enablers

z_2 = Government Policy

$y_1 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$

$y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i$
----- (i)

$y_2 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$

$y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i$ --
----- (ii)

$$y_3 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + e_i \dots$$

----- (iii)

$$y_4 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_4 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + e_i \dots$$

----- (iv)

$$y_5 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_5 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + e_i \dots$$

----- (v)

$$Y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + e_i \dots$$

----- (vi)

$$Y = f(X^*Z_1)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 Z_1 + \beta_3 X^*Z_1 + \mu_i$$

(vii)

$$Y = f(X^*Z_2)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 Z_2 + \beta_3 X^*Z_2 + \mu_i$$

(viii)

β_0 = Constant of the equation or constant term

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Parameters to be estimated

e_i = Error or stochastic term

4.0 Literature Review

Entrepreneurship education is the process of knowledge, skill, competency and attitude development which aims to maximize the effectiveness of the entrepreneurial capacity building (Toth-Pajor et al.,

2023). Entrepreneurship education is the process of professional application of qualitative entrepreneurial teaching and learning, that has to do with teaching students how to build their own dreams thereby transforming into turbo-charged business owners (job creators, employers and entrepreneurs) instead of job seekers (employees) with the innate passion and innovative practical skills to produce unmet market needs through newly created ventures (Oluwasanya, 2026). Similarly, Nguyen and Nguyen (2023) argue that entrepreneurship education enhances the entrepreneurial capacity of students and helps form and develop entrepreneurial intentions. The universities' educational interventions help spread entrepreneurial thinking; thus, they contribute to entrepreneurial capacity building in the economy. Entrepreneurship education is a research focused process enabling us to investigate the most favourable education process to produce graduates in order to transform them into individuals who have life skills (Mico & Cungu, 2023). More study is being done on the subject which has led to a rapid expansion of the entrepreneurship education field. In addition to expanding its exposure in general education, this has strengthened theoretical and methodological rigour (Sreenivasan & Suresh, 2023). This is attributed to the fact that entrepreneurship education and training provides individuals with the ability to recognize commercial

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opportunities, self-esteem, knowledge and skills to act on them (Mico et al., 2023). Entrepreneurship education is any pedagogical program or process of education for entrepreneurial attitudes and abilities (Yan et al., 2023). Thus, entrepreneurship education influences the acquisition of entrepreneurial knowledge on the gender, age, school ownership and socio-educational level of the parents (Nunez-Canal et al., 2023). Pedagogically, entrepreneurship education for prospective educational leaders empowered course lecturers to emphasise creativity, innovation, employment creation, and educational entrepreneurial leadership when teaching (Manaseh et al., 2022). Research conducted by Zen et al. (2023) studied implications of entrepreneurship education as a field of study for advancing research and practice. It is in realization of this fact that many universities worldwide have included entrepreneurship specializations in their academic service delivery, either as distinct programs or as courses within business studies (Mohammad et al., 2023). This reflects the expansion of entrepreneurship specialization, and the urgent need of individuals and companies to understand and leverage it in an increasingly competitive global economy. Therefore, higher educational institutions play an important role in ensuring that entrepreneurship education develops the potential of students as well as encourages entrepreneurial activities and

subsequently helps them to choose an entrepreneurial career over others (Othman et al., 2022). Students need to know how classroom learning can inspire entrepreneurial practice. Nowadays, entrepreneurship is a subject that attracts attention for all majors in higher education. However, the determination of learning outcomes in entrepreneurship education is still debatable, especially in non-entrepreneurship majors (Rahman et al., 2022). Entrepreneurship education seems to be attracting significant attention from academia, government and the larger society in recent years. Most importantly, government and other stakeholders are assiduously working towards equipping learners for successful entrepreneurial endeavours. There is no doubt that universities play an important role through paradigm shift in qualitative entrepreneurial teaching and learning towards steering and stimulating entrepreneurial behaviours in learners to think entrepreneurially out of the box towards achieving consistently consistent entrepreneurial success in a variety of setting. (Oluwasanya, 2025). Entrepreneurship education additionally offers more practical teachings in stimulating entrepreneurial behaviour and acquisition of skills relevant to the needs of the changing operational milieu (Musa, 2025). Incontrovertibly, entrepreneurship education is taught in all of the study programs at the universities in Nigeria. The goal is for the university to inject

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entrepreneurial thinking and behaviours in their learners (Musa, 2025). Entrepreneurial behaviour is a broad concept which focuses on the nurturing the nature of learners and talent development and the design of an enterprising learning institution (Musa, 2025). It relates to possibility mentality with the requisite bulldozing spirit and turbo-charged passion to make things happen entrepreneurially (Musa, 2025). Thus, entrepreneurship education seeks to provide students with the entrepreneurial behaviours, passion and to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of setting (Musa, 2025). To be entrepreneurial, venturesome or enterprising is to be focused with positive mindset. It is having a paradigm shift, requisite skills and turbo-charged possibility mentality to create and seize business opportunities so as to translate into new venture creation and new products or services to the market profitably (Oluwasanya, 2025). It follows therefore that steering and stimulating entrepreneurial behaviours has three necessary conditions, these being: the absence of limiting belief, identifying and activating entrepreneurial opportunity mindset and passion to create new outlets (Oluwasanya, 2025). Without the simultaneous existence of these three pre-requisite conditions, entrepreneurial, enterprising or venturesome behaviours will not be eventuated. It is in realization of the important role of entrepreneurship plays in economic

development that government introduced entrepreneurship education at various levels of educational system in Nigeria (Musa, 2025). The expectation is that the students who are exposed to qualitative entrepreneurial teaching and learning programs will think entrepreneurially out of the box with possibility mentality and requisite entrepreneurial behaviours towards achieving positive entrepreneurial outcomes (Oluwasanya, 2025). What is not clear however is how the learners perceive the application and stimulation of entrepreneurial teaching and learning programs (Musa, 2025). Learner's perception of entrepreneurial behaviours has become a key concern for researchers in the areas of entrepreneurship (Musa, 2025). Oluwasanya (2025) asserted that entrepreneurial behaviour is an individual's paradigm shift and ability to think out of the box entrepreneurially to identify unmet market needs and create an outlet to transform them into products and services for customers and consumers. Therefore, with entrepreneurship education in place, graduates have the ability to acquire some entrepreneurial traits which can influence the graduate's entrepreneurial behaviour (Ediagbonya, 2013). Over the last two decades, researchers have sought to determine the relationship between entrepreneurship education support programmes and entrepreneurial behaviour (Wang et al., 2019).

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Entrepreneurial behaviour influences decision making and contributes to raising organizational performance (Bezerra et al., 2023). Several studies have found that the ecosystem factors in SMEs are capable of impacting behaviour of entrepreneurs (Adeel et al., 2023). As students in university happen to be the carbon copy of the society, they equally turn out to exhibit talents that precede action and an unswerving attitude towards entrepreneurial behaviours (Sampene et al., 2022). Thus, behaviour associated with entrepreneurship makes the major contribution to surviving external challenges. It also has the decisive impact of achieving competitive advantages. There are a few factors that influence entrepreneurial behaviour when starting a new venture. An individual should have confidence in themselves to show an entrepreneurial attitude: without having self-confidence, it is not possible to become an entrepreneur (Akter & Iqbal, 2022). Entrepreneurial behaviour is defined as identifying possibilities and putting good ideas into action (Wang et al., 2019). Resultantly, encouraging entrepreneurial behaviour has become a major aim in entrepreneurship. According to Othman et al. (2022), entrepreneurial behaviour is a process of action or deed that has been done towards the establishment of a business. Entrepreneurship education can alter students' perceptions about the difficulties of starting their own business, a

concept known as perceived behavioural control (Alferaih, 2022). This aspect emphasizes that many behaviours are not totally within volitional control which is reflected in prior practices and the existence or lack of opportunities and resources. Finally, perceived behavioural control measures how easy or difficult it is to start a new behaviour and how much control one has over their behaviour. -In order to better understand behaviour, psychology has created models that can be used to make predictions about future conduct (GEM, 2022). An assessment of the influence of entrepreneurship education has made use of theory of planned behaviour (TPB) (Jin, 2022; Zhai et al., 2022). TPB is a useful model for analyzing behaviour at least partially under free will control (Zhang et al., 2022). For the theory, it is assumed that one's actions are best explained by one's desire to strive to carry out those actions (Sampene et al., 2022). To put it another way, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioural control influence intentions and perceived benefits of a particular action impact one's attitude. Asika and James (2022) posited further that entrepreneurial behaviour can be viewed in various constructs of such as entrepreneurial Innovative Behaviour (EIB), Entrepreneurial Proactive Behaviour (EPB), Entrepreneurial Risk-Taking Behaviour (ERT) and Entrepreneurial Cognitive Behaviour (ECB). Individuals' state of mind can transform their acts into actual behaviours when they are

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“intentionally” doing them. Also, Inegbedion et al. (2019) entrepreneurial behaviour is a subset of entrepreneurial activities concerned with understanding, predicting and influencing individual behaviour in entrepreneurial settings. Entrepreneurial behaviour is explained as a whole of all processes and task that includes identifying opportunities and establishing a new venture. It is made up of entrepreneurial mindsets and behaviour that is used in the process of identifying opportunities, recognizing those opportunities, creating a new venture, introducing a product or service and growth of the new venture.

5.0 Theoretical Model

This study will be adopting multiple regression analysis. The assumptions of multiple regression are there must be a linear relationship between the outcome variable and the independent variables, multiple regression assumes that the residuals are normally distributed, further it assumes that the independent variables entrepreneurship education were not highly correlated with each other; and finally, that the variance of error terms were similar across the value of the independent variables.

The independent variable in this study is entrepreneurship education which is measured by sub-variables of entrepreneurial culture, entrepreneurial mindsets, entrepreneurial capacities, entrepreneurial attitudes and entrepreneurial skills. Measures of

entrepreneurial culture includes theoretical, pedagogical, didactical and practical environment that encourages talent development, nurturing the innate qualities, innovation and risk taking by learners. Entrepreneurial mindset includes creativity, innovation and taking opportunities that leads to organizational wealth creation and success and that this type of mindset enables entrepreneurs to make realistic decisions when faced with uncertainties. Entrepreneurial capacities include ability to perceive, choose, shape and synchronize internal and external conditions for the enterprise exploration and exploitation. Entrepreneurial attitudes include the mindset or disposition that drives individuals to pursue entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurial skills include activities taken by learners (potential entrepreneurs) driven by qualitative teaching and innovation which are directed at having the quality and requisite skills to succeed as an entrepreneur. The dependent variable in this study is entrepreneurial behaviour which is divided into: possibility mentality, proactive abilities, turbo-charged passion, innovativeness and creativity, risk-taking attributes. Measures of possibility mentality include having a mindset of possibilities by exploring what can be possible and transiting what you can see right in front of you. Proactive abilities include ability to think ahead by anticipating challenges. Turbo-charged passion includes enthusiasm, energy

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and intense drive that drives you towards stated goals and objectives. Innovativeness and creativity include thinking out of the box by coming up with fresh ideas and turning imagination to reality. Risk-taking attributes include the qualities that drives someone to take calculated risks by embracing uncertainty and stepping out of your comfort zone. Regressionally, the econometric model for this study using multiple regression will be:

$$PM = a_0 + \beta_1 LS + \beta_2 LF + \beta_3 LA + \beta_4 LI + \beta_5 LC + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (i)}$$

$$RS = a_0 + \beta_1 LS + \beta_2 LF + \beta_3 LA + \beta_4 LI + \beta_5 LC + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (ii)}$$

$$RP = a_0 + \beta_1 LS + \beta_2 LF + \beta_3 LA + \beta_4 LI + \beta_5 LC + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (iii)}$$

$$AA = a_0 + \beta_1 LS + \beta_2 LF + \beta_3 LA + \beta_4 LI + \beta_5 LC + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (iv)}$$

$$PA = a_0 + \beta_1 LS + \beta_2 LF + \beta_3 LA + \beta_4 LI + \beta_5 LC + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (v)}$$

$$EB = a_0 + \beta_1 EB_{EO} + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (vi)}$$

$$EB = a_0 + \beta_1 LS + \beta_2 LF + \beta_3 LA + \beta_4 LI + \beta_5 LC + e_i * (BE) \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (vii)}$$

$$EB = a_0 + \beta_1 LS + \beta_2 LF + \beta_3 LA + \beta_4 LI + \beta_5 LC + e_i * (GP) \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (viii)}$$

Where;

PM, PA, TP, IC and RA are Dependent variables
 EC, EM, EC, EA and ES are Independent variables

a_0 = Constant term

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Parameters to be estimated

e = Stochastic error term

EC = Entrepreneurial Culture

EM = Entrepreneurial Mindsets

EC = Entrepreneurial Capacities

EA = Entrepreneurial Attitudes

ES = Entrepreneurial Skills.

EE = Entrepreneurship Education

PM = Possibility Mentality

PA = Proactive Abilities

TP = Turbo-Charged Passion

IC = Innovativeness and Creativity

RA = Risk-taking Attributes

EB = Entrepreneurial Behaviour.

EE = Educational Enablers

GP = Government Policy

6.0 Research Methodology

This study was carried out in selected private universities in Kwara State, Nigeria (University of Offa, Summit University, Offa, Landmark University, Omu-Aran and Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin) as the population of the study. This is because they are duly accredited by the National University Commission and they offer entrepreneurship as general courses at various levels. The choice of Kwara state for the study is based on the proximity to the researcher as well as opportunity to generalize findings. The study adopts descriptive survey research design which facilitates the use of a structured research instrument in obtaining data for the analysis. This research design is appropriate for this study because it allows the researcher to explain and translate the response

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from respondents to determining the link between the dependent variable, entrepreneurial behaviours (possibility mentality, proactive abilities, turbo-charged passion, innovativeness and creativity, risk-taking attributes) and the independent variable, entrepreneurship education dimensions (entrepreneurial culture, entrepreneurial mindsets, entrepreneurial capacities, entrepreneurial attitudes and entrepreneurial skills). It also provides data that will represent the perception and view of people across a large geographical area which in this case are the educators and learners of the selected private universities in Kwara State, Nigeria. Furthermore, the adoption of the survey research design is not only to get the reality of events but also to focus on the discovery of interwoven factors, with particular reference to the link between dependent and independent variables. The adoption of this design is consistent with the studies of (Shabbir, 2018; Waiganjo & Njeru; 2015; Olajide, 2015; Awino, 2013). The population of the study in the four selected private universities in Kwara State, Nigeria. is 13025. A sample size of 375 comprising of learners formed the respondents for the study. Multi-stage sampling technique which involved purposive sampling, stratified random sampling and simple random sampling techniques was used to select the respondents according to their designation. The first stage involved purposive sampling which will be used

to select the universities used for this study. The second stage involved stratified sampling technique which will be used to categorize the study population (learners) in the four selected private universities into different academic years. Hence, learners in these universities regardless of their course of study will be grouped into five according to their academic year of study. This will enhance the identification of sub-groups within the study population and also create a sample which adequately represented these sub-groups (Yount, 2006). Questionnaire was used to collect data relating to independent, dependent and moderating variables which were validated through a pilot study using Crown Hill University now known as Ojaja University, Eiyenkorin and Lens University, Ilemona, Kwara State for the sake of convenience and the fact that the university though not part of the study population are duly accredited by the National University Commission and offer entrepreneurship as general courses at various levels. Entrepreneurship education is the independent variable and its sub-variables are entrepreneurial culture, entrepreneurial mindsets, entrepreneurial capacities, entrepreneurial attitudes and entrepreneurial skills. The dependent variable is entrepreneurial behaviour and its sub-variables are possibility mentality, proactive abilities, turbo-charged passion, innovativeness and creativity, risk-taking attributes. The

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questions were closed ended on a five-point Likert scale. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze data with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The questionnaire design is in three parts: part A is for demographic data of respondents while parts B and C are to obtain concise and precise information required for the analysis of the independent, dependent and moderating variables respectively. To test the reliability of the instrument, the researcher administered the instrument to ten senior members of staff and for the purpose of evaluating the effectiveness of the instrument employed. After a period of two weeks, the same instruments were re-administered to the same respondents to determine its reliability. The result of the reliability using SPSS, a statistical software package reveals that their Cronbach's alpha is above 0.7 threshold (Asika, 2004, Biserka & Dragana, 2012). This indicates that the consistency instrument (questionnaire) can be a reliable tool to measure the two concepts (entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial behaviour) consistently.

7.0 Sources of Data

The information for this study was collected through primary sources because it helps to obtain information in its raw state directly from the respondents making the information original, fresh and reliable. Primary data was collected from a representative sample which are the final year business administration

students of selected state universities. Data collected was used for the purpose for which they are collected. The services of research assistants were employed in order to ensure that the questionnaires for the study were administered to the respondents and then retrieved for the purpose of final analysis. The research assistants will be trained on the objectives of the study and how they can effectively collect the data that was needed for the study. Research assistants were used in order to fast track the collection of data for the study.

8.0 Discussion of Findings

The crux of this study was to examine theoretically and empirically the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial behaviours of learners of private universities in Kwara State, Nigeria by applying the components of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial behaviours of learners in universities in Kwara State, Nigeria with a focus on the four private universities in Kwara State that are duly accredited by the National University Commission and offer entrepreneurship as general courses at various levels. They are: University of Offa, Summit University, Offa, Landmark University, Omu-Aran and Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Kwara State. The theoretical review and summary of findings were designed to achieve these objectives. Many empirical studies such as Al-Qadasi et al., (2024); Hou et al., (2023); Zen et

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al., (2023); Mico & Cungu, (2023); Bezerra et al., (2023); Adeel et al., (2023); Sampene et al., (2022); Akter & Iqbal, (2022); Othman et al., (2022); Alferaih, (2022); Asika and James (2022); Wang et al., (2019). The results show that the employed components of entrepreneurship education have pertinent contribution to the steering and stimulation of entrepreneurial behaviours.

The theoretical review and summary of findings were designed to achieve these objectives. Specifically, the study surveys the influence of entrepreneurship education variables (entrepreneurial culture, entrepreneurial mindsets, entrepreneurial capacities, entrepreneurial attitudes and entrepreneurial skills) on each of the entrepreneurial behaviour variables (possibility mentality, proactive abilities, turbo-charged passion, innovativeness and creativity, risk-taking attributes.) in tandem with the analysis of the moderating effect of educational enablers and government policy. In general, and consistence with previous studies, entrepreneurship education was found to have a statistically significant influence on each entrepreneurial behaviour's variables (possibility mentality, proactive abilities, turbo-charged passion, innovativeness and creativity, risk-taking attributes). For the moderating variables (educational enablers and government policy), the result of this study showed that only government policy has a statistically significant moderating effect on the relationship between

entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial behaviours. The empirical results of the study revealed that the components of entrepreneurship education have positive statistically significant effect on entrepreneurial behaviours of higher education institutions Nigeria-wide. Thus, qualitative entrepreneurship education teaching and learning focused at steering and stimulating entrepreneurial behaviour should explode into a vast multitude of higher education institution-wide offerings in terms of pedagogy, didactics and contents itself so that it permeates and percolates learner's passion, spirit and commitment from the pre-cradle (primary education), cradle (secondary education) and the post-cradle (tertiary education) so as to produce turbo-charged entrepreneurs who think out of the box with possibility mentality to make things happen entrepreneurially (Musa and Oluwasanya, 2026).

9.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- a. There is need to consistently institutionalise talent development, venturesome/enterprising culture, nurturing the nature of potential entrepreneurs (learners) synergy and team working.
- b. There is a need for a paradigm shift in the pedagogical approaches adopted in Nigerian higher education institutions from being largely

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theoretical to experiential and practical approaches.

c. Potential entrepreneurs (learners) should have the opportunity to engage in activities outside their core curriculum or as an extension to their learning. Examples include competitions, internships, workshops and entrepreneurial boot camps, action research and community-based enterprise, where students feel their actions are real and have an impact locally;

d. learning by case studies and group projects be encouraged in tandem with the development of business incubators that will enable students to graduate into business start-ups; students be attached to businesses and help in identifying the challenges faced by the particular business and propose workable solutions;

e. inviting tested entrepreneurs to give learners an insight into the range of different occupations in the local area and visits to successful entrepreneurial firms; and listening to guest speakers from entrepreneurial firms;

f. Effective teaching methods such as invitation of guest speakers, individual and group projects and particularly business simulations activities should be adopted by Nigerian higher education institutions to stimulate students' interest and business start-ups.

g. Business start-ups by potential entrepreneurs (learners) should be a

prerequisite activity of an entrepreneurship programme because it increases the likelihood of students engaging in entrepreneurial activities at graduation and they should also be provided with adequate information about starting a new business and about business trends in order to minimize future risks and maximize success rates.

h. Management of higher education institutions should lay much emphasis on training and re-training of the caretakers (entrepreneurship educators) on the peculiarity and modalities involved in delivery of entrepreneurship modules and courses and lock-in with non-governmental organizations and banks to give soft loans/grants to entrepreneurship educators for experiential training through establishing and running their own businesses thereby becoming academic entrepreneurs (Acapreneurs). This will enable them to practices what they preach (teaching by doing) acquire practical experience from their own initiatives for onward transmission to the students.

i. Entrepreneurship educators should ensure to utilise their experience and skill to mentor and stimulate Lerner's entrepreneurial behaviour and commitment to entrepreneurial learning.

j. Provision of adequate educational enablers like appropriate instruction materials, technology, equipment, aesthetically pleasing

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environment and support services to ensure relevance to the Nigeria situation.

k. University support systems in Nigerian higher education institutions should be characterized by adequate enablers and initiatives such as technology patenting and commercialization, seed funding, business mentoring and business incubators to motivate

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l. Government should set machinery in motion to provide an enabling environment for entrepreneurship. This includes formulation of policies, provision of good roads, pipe borne water, electricity etc.

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